

ROLE OF THE BIONICS ON THE JEWELERS END ECODESIGN**Kambarova Oydin Sobirjanovna**

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Abstract: *In this article, the article focuses on the fundamental role and evolving of costume in human ethnography (the material and spiritual culture), its material and spiritual culture, social relations and family life, the disclaimer of its nature-like characteristics and the influence on the development of modern trendstyle in the world of the clothings.*

Folk costume as one of its most important types of decorative and applied arts is of the greatest interest and completely embodies the diverse connection of a person with the outside world. A unique type – its design – has been described as one of the most dynamic kinds of this entire variety, all changes to society are reflected in it through using current signs and symbols. Responsible attitude to nature, a search for ways of preserving the environment through design clothing, unique ways to increase the eco-system and accurate pollution control due to the use by natural and eco-materials in fabrics and cl.

The laws of shaping in design of the national costume in a context of "Green" theory and bionics together with the history method allow to consider the evolution and accumulation of knowledge about biological principles and formulate its significance for.

Keywords: Bionics, environments friendliness, nature conformability.

Today processes of integration, mechanisation and standardization are not only characteristic that help large corporations to achieve quick result but also important factors leading to sad conclusions which manifested themselves not only as a formation of modern clothing, no also in other areas. We must admit that a great number of objects that have already lost the individuality together with low-qualities artificial materials that appeared recently caused no positive emotions and asthetic pleasure, but also have a serious negative impact on Human perception.

A problem of how to get rid off the harmful effects on a human being, or the search for an alternative way of its leveling, is becoming a painful one. Ecology conservation ideas, both cultural and scientific, will be fruitful. Among such powerful art forms as television and cinema, there is fashion design. Fashion should be in tune with the environment and concern for nature.

The theme of nature is the subject of study for a number of modern scientific research, and for the designer it serves as an inexhaustible creative source.

At the beginning of the 21st century, awareness and rethinking of the role of man in the world took place, and on the new wave of "green" philosophy, the main principle was a harmonious relationship with nature. Humanity exists because of it, and owes much to it. Any change to our planet has an impact and can be detrimental to both physical, emotional and psychological health of people themselves.

Many young modern designers and sometimes already recognized ones as they say "do not bother." They look through magazines, go to fashion shows, watch fashion by fashion channel and take ideas from other designers for their future creations. Certainly, not in pure form by copying, but by slightly changing the color, fabric, design of the product. Thus, they make an attempt to create a completely new product of creativity. This is a well-known and common method of work. The most promising would be the creation of new materials with new operational properties that have the ability to acquire desired properties, as well as the development of

harmless and waste-free production technologies in order to obtain environmentally friendly products.

From the point of view of aesthetics, the abundance of details, iconic systems, the richest women's suit, in which there is a conditional division into "tiers" can be of great value. Researcher B. A. Rybakov presents a costume as a model of the Universe, where symbols of ornamental patterns correspond to different tiers. So, for example, at the very top, the ornaments reflect the symbols of the sky, on the upper edge of the clothes are birds, rain; on the lower tier - vegetation, seeds and symbols of the earth [3].

If you make a digression into history, then in antiquity, there was a great influence on the analysis of the process of human visual perception of objects of nature in the absence of an artificial environment, which resulted in an exceptionally bionic characteristic of the form and content of the costume. The symbiosis of nature and technology of clothing is manifested most clearly.

The specific needs of people in the tissues and other materials for the manufacture of clothing evolved over time and under the influence of many factors - natural, climatic, historical, ethnic, socio-economic. The costume is from its inception to its most recent forms, a social sign distinguishing one class of society from another, from one nation to another, one profession from another, one individuality from another, etc. Folk costume (clothing and jewelry) is a complex structure, including numerous types of upper and lower clothing, hats, shoes, jewelry. The formation of the traditional costume of the peoples in the world is associated with the use of products of a whole complex of various types of folk decorative and applied arts that form its ensemble. [5,6]

The commitment to the environment, naturalness and uniqueness have made eco-design, eco-fashion megapopular areas in many countries where there are enough resources and raw materials for it. A boom swept the world, ecofriendly products attract the attention of consumers who care about their health and are not involved in environmental pollution, they make the choice that, long before the

factories, was made by nature itself. Communication with nature is fashionable, to be “eco-friendly”, ethical in relation to nature - has long been considered of good taste, everything recognizes the laws of harmony. Naturalness becomes even something elite, while not necessarily, an object made of valuable wood or alloy, and if the material is accepted as rare, disappearing in nature, it is unethical, and therefore not environmentally friendly. [8,9]

The theme of nature is the subject of study for a number of modern scientific research, and for the designer it serves as an inexhaustible creative source. Costume design is one of the most mobile types of design, all changes in the life of society are reflected in it through the costume language: the use of current signs and symbols allows you to speak the modern language of fashion.

Eco-design clothing is not just fashion. There are a number of problems that are solvable only with the effective promotion of the idea of sustainable development and the introduction of an institutions to foster an ecological and healthy lifestyle. Modern production should minimize the harm caused to the environment, making a choice in favor of creating beautiful, practical and convenient things made from local materials according to long-established technologies. [10]

Bionic structures shaping the costume make it possible to endlessly balance between artificial and natural form, they define new conditions for the industrial production of garments. Clothing is an essential part of the culture of humans along with its traditions, customs, music, etc.

As a result of copying the structures of nature, systems can be created, firstly, performing specified functions, secondly, performing these functions with the highest possible perfection, and thirdly, being organically coherent spatial systems. Consequently, this approach involves the identification of the laws of the formation and functioning of the systems of nature, the specifics of the structural-functional relations and the subsequent use of these laws in the design of a suit.

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